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My Friends, Don't Be Fooled by "AI"!

Sam Khosravifard · 3 min read · 6 days ago

Facts on eDNA & DNA Barcoding Services?!

A decorative image created with the assistance of Gemini

I had a quick chat with a friend a few weeks ago, which motivated me to write this piece. Before getting started, let me get this straight first: some people use the terms “AI” or “ChatGPT” as they are shorter and easier to say, instead of saying “Large Language Model (LLM).” Well, that’s quite understandable! LLMs are a type of AI; not all AI systems are LLMs. So, this story focuses on LLMs, not AI in general, as the title suggests.

Now the story begins: some of my friends constantly fact-check everything they hear, even in the middle of a conversation. They used to rely on Wikipedia for answers, but recently, ChatGPT has taken its place. While their interest in accuracy is admirable, interruption for constant fact-checking derails real-time discussions. (Maybe this is why some prefer voice messages over a real-time conversation. Isn't this exactly what Noah Harari warns about in his new book, *Nexus*?)

A few weeks ago, my friend and I were discussing species identification techniques. I listed several conventional (or maybe old traditional) methods that the private and non-profit sectors used, like direct observation or capturing species, both of which are labour-intensive and highly disruptive to the organisms and their habitat. He cut me off and added that DNA sampling is a common practice here in Canada, where I live. Then, I explained the differences between e-DNA and DNA barcoding, expressing my doubt about their practicality and plurality in private environmental consulting companies. For a few seconds, I felt the WhatsApp call had dropped. But he was busy consulting ChatGPT.

"Both eDNA and DNA barcoding are commonly used in the private sector in Canada, particularly by environmental consultant companies," he erupted.

"I'm not so sure," I replied.

After the call, I started researching eDNA and DNA barcoding services, prompting ChatGPT and Gemini. I asked whether these techniques are commonly used in the private sector, and both language models confirmed their popularity. I then prompted ChatGPT to list environmental consultant companies in Canada conducting DNA barcoding and eDNA analysis, and asked Gemini to list 10 companies which provide such services. By reviewing the websites of these companies, I found that only one explicitly mentioned

DNA barcoding in its services. Another company had a few articles related to eDNA, nothing more.

Next, I searched the terms using Google, like the good old times, and found companies and labs offering eDNA and DNA barcoding services, but not those suggested by ChatGPT or Gemini. Still, I'm not sure that these techniques are as widespread or popular among private consulting companies, especially the small ones, as the LLMs claim. Perhaps experts can provide an accurate answer; no machines.

Anyway, my friends! AI language models are not omniscient, so please don't believe everything they say.

Here's an interesting article about tracking animals:

<https://news.stanford.edu/stories/2020/01/tracking-animals-dna>

AI

E Dna

Dna

Biodiversity

ChatGPT

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